

English Phonological Analysis: Revealing Sound Structure and Patterns

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ABSTRAK

Fonologi adalah metode yang ampuh untuk menguraikan hubungan rumit antara bahasa dan struktur bunyi. Melalui penyelidikannya, para ilmuwan memperoleh sedikit pengetahuan tentang bagaimana suara disampaikan, dilihat, dan dikoordinasikan dalam dialek, yang pada akhirnya menambah pemahaman yang lebih mendalam tentang gagasan utama korespondensi manusia. Dalam fonologi, kita mengalami bunyi-bunyi representatif yang merupakan refleksi mental. Mereka bertindak sebagai gambaran atau gambar yang mewakili suara asli yang kita dengar dalam bahasa. Walaupun bunyi-bunyian tersebut bukan merupakan replika fisik dari bunyi-bunyian tersebut, bunyi-bunyian simbolik ini merupakan konstruksi mental yang membantu kita dalam mempelajari dan menganalisis cara kerja bunyi-bunyi bahasa. Dalam penelitian ini, metode penelitian digunakan. Seperti yang ditunjukkan oleh pemahaman subjektif operator Kirk dan Mill pada awalnya didasarkan pada persepsi subjektif dan bukan persepsi kuantitatif. Fonologi mengkhawatirkan informasi semantik semacam ini. Fonologi mempelajari bagaimana bunyi ujaran membentuk sistem dan pola dalam bahasa manusia. Fonetik menyediakan sarana untuk mendeskripsikan fonologi suatu bahasa, yaitu sistem dan pola bunyi ujaran.

ABSTRACT

Phonology is a powerful method for deciphering the intricate connection between language and sound structure. Through its investigation, scientists gain bits of knowledge into how sounds are delivered, saw, and coordinated inside dialects, eventually adding to a more profound comprehension of the major idea of human correspondence. In phonology, we experience representative sounds that are mental reflections. They act as portrayals or images that represent the genuine sounds we hear in language. Although they are not exact physical replicas of those sounds, these symbolic sounds are mental constructs that assist us in studying and analyzing how language sounds work. In this study, research methods were utilized. As indicated by Kirk and Mill operator subjective comprehension was at first in light of subjective perceptions as opposed to quantitative perceptions. Phonology is worried about this sort of semantic information. Phonology studies how speech sounds form systems and patterns in human language. Phonetics provides the means for describing a language's phonology, which is the system and pattern of speech sounds.

PENDAHULUAN

The force of phonology lies in its capacity to dissect and comprehend what the construction of sounds means for language. Phonology investigates the complex connection between discourse sounds, their creation (articulatory phonetics), insight (hear-able phonetics), and the hidden physical science included (acoustic phonetics). By concentrating on phonology, scientists gain experience in how sounds are framed, heard, and addressed in various dialects. (Maharani, 2023)

Additionally, phonology examines how speech sounds are arranged in language. It explores how these sounds are purposely coordinated into etymological structures, similar to phonemes, syllables, and phonological standards. Phonology, for instance, looks at how sounds can be joined, how they connect, and how they work together and affect one another. Understanding the construction and examples of a language requires a comprehension of the job that phonology plays in it. Language specialists can discover the rules that govern the arrangement and association of discourse sounds by investigating phonological frameworks. A deeper comprehension of language construction and variation across linguistic contexts is made possible by this knowledge.

The investigation of phonology has expansive ramifications. It assists specialists with examining the exceptional qualities of dialects, distinguishing language-explicit phonological examples, and looking at them across changed etymological networks. Furthermore, phonological examination supports the

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improvement of viable language-showing strategies, language instruction procedures, and programmed discourse acknowledgment frameworks. The investigation of phonology is an integral asset for disentangling the many-sided connection between sound construction and language. Through its investigation, scientists gain bits of knowledge into how sounds are delivered, seen, and coordinated inside dialects, eventually adding to a more profound comprehension of the major idea of human correspondence. In phonology, we experience representative sounds that are mental reflections. They act as portrayals or images that represent the genuine sounds we hear in language. These representative sounds are mental developments that help us study and break down how language sounds work, yet they are not the specific actual copies of those sounds. (Maharani, 2023).

Three primary perspectives are covered by the in-depth study of speech sounds known as phonetics: articulatory, auditory, and acoustic. The study of articulatory phonetics focuses on the physical processes by which the tongue, lips, and vocal cords make speech sounds. To better understand how our ears process and interpret the numerous acoustic signals that include speech, auditory phonetics investigates how these sounds are perceived by the human auditory system. Last but not least, acoustic phonetics studies the behavior of speech sounds in terms of frequencies, sound waves, and other acoustic aspects.

Phonology, on the other hand, is concerned with how speech sounds are arranged inside particular languages. To construct logical language systems, it investigates the systematic organization of these many speech sounds. Phonology studies how sounds combine to produce meaningful units such as words and sentences, as well as the relationships and interactions between various sounds in a language. Furthermore, phonology investigates the ways in which sounds interact with one another to produce phonological processes or phonetic alterations. In essence, phonology aims to comprehend the laws and structures governing the sound systems of various languages, offering insights into the many distinctive ways that speakers of a given language use and arrange speech sounds.

RESEARCH METHOD

Subjective examination strategies were utilized in this exploration. Kirk and Miller assert that qualitative comprehension was initially founded on qualitative rather than quantitative observations. They then characterize subjective methods as a specific custom in the sociologies that is founded on seeing individuals as would be natural for them and connecting with these individuals in their language and significance.

Subjective exploration has characteristics that separate it from different kinds of examination. As indicated by Strauss and Corbin, subjective exploration is a sort of revelation that can't be accomplished utilizing factual strategies or other estimation evaluation techniques. By and large, subjective exploration can be utilized to examine public activity, history, conduct, hierarchical functionalization, social exercises, and different points. One of the advantages of utilizing a subjective methodology is that scientists have found that this strategy can be utilized to find and comprehend what is taken cover behind peculiarities that are in some cases challenging to appropriately comprehend.

Sugiyono, on the other hand, explains that subjective exploration strategies are research strategies based on interpretivism or postpositivism that are used to focus on the typical condition of items. These strategies use the scientist as the primary instrument, triangulation (a combination of perception, meetings, and documentation) to gather information, and research is subjective.

RESULT

Defenition Of Phonology

We as often as possible have instincts about language without knowing where they come from or precisely how to communicate them. Phonological information isn't something we can get to and talk about inside and out. Anyway, the data is there. "fwil is not possible (as the asterisk conventionally shows)" is an example of a possible but nonexistent word, and most English speakers will agree with this. Then again, full is a precise hole that is brought about by the principles of the English sound framework, though swil is an unintentional hole in the jargon. In any case, English speakers are not purposely aware of those standards, and are significantly fantastical to educate an etymologist getting some data concerning those words that the shortage of fuel reflects the unsuitable nature of word-beginning consonant groupings, or bundles, with [fn-] in English: the more plausible reaction is that swil 'sounds great' (and accepting at least for now that you're lucky, your source will convey similar words like sniff or slice to back up her dispute), nonetheless, that full 'essentially sounds wrong. (McMahon, 2002).

The phonologist is liable for communicating such speculations in exact terms since, even though the information isn't cognizant, this doesn't imply that it is stunning, irrelevant, or not worth getting. Exactly when you run the ground floor, you don't purposely think 'left gluteus maximus, left foot, right

arm; right gluteus maximus, right foot, left arm' on each arrangement of steps. You're presumably not going to seek after any perceptive decisions at all, underneath the level of expecting to go down-steps regardless; and to some degree, two or three people will know the names of the muscles being referred to. Ending up being deliberately aware of the singular activities included is exceptionally inclined to agitate the general cycle: contemplate what you're doing, and you finish the drop nose-first. This is all outstandingly reminiscent of our ordinary use of correspondence in language.

We choose to talk, and what might be said about, yet the stray pieces of discourse favorable to duction are past our cognizant reach; and pondering what we are talking about, and how we are saying it, is probably going to cause reluctance and dithering, interfering with the progression of familiar discourse instead of further developing matters. Comparative mixes of mental and actual development, interior capacities, and outside input assist kids with creating language and portability (creeping, strolling, and running ground floor). We just become faintly mindful of the intricacy behind our activities when we understand we have delivered a discourse blunder or when we see and hear a youngster battling to say a word or make a stride. As we progress, what we have realized turns out to be simple, familiar, and programmed. Phonologists, similar to anatomists and physiologists, pursue helping us in fathoming the idea of that hidden intricacy and officially depicting what we realize in a specific space yet don't realize we know. (April McMahon, 2002)

The connection between phonetics and phonology is a complicated one, however, we could at first methodology phonology as reduced phonetics. Tiny children, in the chattering stage, produce the entire scope of conceivable human sounds, including a few that they never hear from gatekeepers or family: a youngster in an English-talking environment will startlingly make consonants that are not found in any European language, yet rather are to be viewed as closest to home in an African language, say, or one from the Caucasus. Regardless, that young person will then restrict her extent of sounds from the full human enhancement to simply those found in the language(s) she is hearing and learning and will ensure, while later endeavoring to learn at school another dialect with another sound stock, that she couldn't in any capacity whatsoever produce new sounds she made perfectly typically when several months old.

On the other hand inside a language, unpretentious mechanical examination of discourse uncovers that each utterance of a similar word, even by a similar speaker, will be a small division unique about each other; yet listeners who share that language will easily recognize a similar word for each situation. In this sense, phonetics is an embarrassment of riches because it provides far more information than speakers appear to use or require: all those speakers and each word is unique! Phonology, then again, includes a decrease in the fundamental data, to what speakers and listeners think they are talking about and hearing.

The viewpoint shifts from additional units to less, from gigantic assortment to relative invariance, from total cement to somewhat extract; like contrasting the specific rose I can see from my window, or roses by and large in the entirety of their assortment (dated, rugged, briar; scented or not, red, yellow, stunning pink), to The Rose, a practically great and unique classification to which we can relegate the various genuine variations. There is no need to distinguish between a white dog rose, a massively exaggerated pink cabbage rose, and a novel genetically engineered variety of roses. In terms of language, it's not just that I say tomato and you say tomato; rather, I say tomato, tomato, and tomato, each of which is subtler than the other, but we both believe I said the same thing three times (April McMahon, 2002).

DISCUSSION OF RESULT

Phonology examines the organization of sounds within a language, focusing on how they are combined and utilized in linguistic structures. Unlike phonetics, which analyzes the physical properties of sounds, phonology delves into the abstract representations of sounds and their roles within a language's system. By understanding this distinction, we can appreciate the crucial role of phonology in uncovering the patterns and structures of a language's sound system, shedding light on how sounds are organized to convey meaning in human communication.

The acoustic environment in classrooms can significantly impact the performance of sound-field systems. Poor classroom acoustics hinder clear hearing, affecting students' comprehension of the material being taught. Interestingly, children in classrooms with inferior acoustics notably improved their understanding when the environment was optimized. However, sound-field systems did not provide additional benefits in classrooms with already superior acoustics.

Phonology deals with the abstract, symbolic sounds of language, investigating their patterns and relationships to understand the underlying structures that shape language. Different from phonetics, phonology's focus on linguistic patterns allows us to decipher language complexities. While much attention has been given to the phonological approach in English, it's important to note that the relationship between phonology and grammar may vary across languages. The language-specific nature of

these relationships challenges the universal application of the phonological approach, suggesting that the phonological assignment of grammatical categories may differ in other languages

The study of how sounds in language are arranged is called phonology. Two main aspects of phonology are the focus of our study. One perspective that we consider is the stock of sounds that a language has. For instance, English has sounds that don't happen in French, as well as the other way around. Assuming that one is concentrating on a language that has never been investigated or down on paper, this is a significant area of study.

Another important aspect is examining the rules that dictate the precise pronunciation of each sound and the interactions between sounds. Understanding these principles is crucial for developing writing systems and learning languages. All languages possess internal structure and organization, regardless of the social standing of their speakers. However, without understanding these rules, languages may seem mysterious and difficult.

Transformational Cycle principle within the framework of Chomsky and Halle's (1968) theory of phonology. The principle governs how phonological rules are applied in generating the phonetic shape of an utterance.

The core idea is that phonological rules are not applied linearly to the entire surface structure (represented as bracketed expressions) but rather in a cyclical fashion. The rules are first applied to the largest constituents (maximal phrases) within the structure. Once all applicable rules have been applied to these maximal phrases, the innermost brackets are removed, essentially revealing smaller constituents. The cycle then recommences, targeting the newly exposed largest constituents and continuing until the entire structure has been processed.

Phonological trees, an alternative representation of surface structure, provide further insight. The Transformational Cycle dictates that rules can only be applied to a constituent (represented by a node in the tree) after all the rules have been applied to its subconstituents (branches dominated by the node).

Illustrating the Transformational Cycle with the stress patterns of "blackboard" and "black board." Although the words themselves are identical, their surface structures differ, leading to distinct stress assignments. This exemplifies how the principle accounts for the influence of syntactic structure on phonetic form.

1. The stress pattern of a phrase can be influenced by its grammatical category. In scenario (1a), the entire phrase is treated as a noun, resulting in a specific stress pattern (13). In scenario (1b), the phrase is a noun phrase, leading to a different stress pattern (21). The rules governing stress apply first to individual words like "black" and "board" before considering the entire phrase.
2. Imagine we have a rule that says short words with one syllable (monosyllabic) have the emphasis (stress) placed on the vowel sound. If we apply this rule to the sentence structures we mentioned earlier (referring to point 1), then take away the unnecessary brackets working from the inside out, we end up with the simplified versions (referring to point 3a and 3b) written in brackets.
3. When they place the strongest emphasis, all the other stresses in the word automatically become a little weaker. This way, they don't need separate rules to weaken stresses, it just happens automatically.
4. This rule says that the strongest emphasis (primary stress) goes on a vowel that already has some emphasis within the word. This is especially true for nouns.
5. Rule (4) posits primary stress placement on a vowel already bearing primary stress within a noun, contingent upon the presence of a subsequent primary-stressed vowel. Conversely, Rule (5) assigns primary stress to a primary-stressed vowel when preceded by another primary-stressed vowel within a noun phrase."
6. We designate Rule (4) as the "Compound Rule" and Rule (5) as the "Nuclear Stress Rule" for clarity in future reference. The appropriate application of these rules relies on the bracketed surface structure representation of the word. The syntactic category labels within these brackets are crucial for determining the correct rule selection. Determining the stress contour for "blackboard" may necessitate an additional rule to demote the secondary stress on the second syllable to tertiary stress. This process can be represented as (Co representing a sequence of zero or more consonants)
7. The system refines the initial rules (Compound Rule and Nuclear Stress Rule) for wider application. This rule now applies not just to compound nouns but also to compound adjectives (e.g., "heartbroken") and verbs (e.g., "air-condition"). In other words, it works for all word types. This rule isn't limited to noun phrases anymore. It can be used for any phrase that isn't a single word category, like verb phrases ("read the book"), adjective phrases ("eager to please"), and even entire sentences ("John left").
8. Rule 8 Put the main emphasis (primary stress) on a vowel that already has emphasis within any word type (except nouns, adjectives, or verbs).

9. The passage proposes expanding the applicability of the previously introduced Compound and Nuclear Stress Rules. This rule now assigns primary stress to a vowel already carrying emphasis within any lexical category (nouns, verbs, adjectives) or within a bracketed structure that doesn't represent these categories (phrases).
10. The excerpt references a notation system employing bracketed numerals to represent stress levels. For instance, "[1 stress]" signifies primary stress. VINA Syllable Structure: This notation captures the potential syllable structure of a word. "V" denotes a vowel, and "N" represents a consonant.
11. Is a contraction for a grouping of rules of the structure
12. Rule format where a symbol gains specific qualities (Y) if it meets a certain condition (X) and another general requirement (Z) is satisfied. The concepts introduced so far have been proven successful in analysing stress patterns in words.
13. When creating derivations, it is possible to strictly adhere to an ordered sequence of rules without losing generality, as opposed to an unordered set or one ordered on a different principle.

Linear ordering allows for more comprehensive expressions of grammatical processes. Neither of these statements is a necessary fact; rather, they constitute an intriguing and, at the moment, rather well-confirmed empirical hypothesis. We shall accept the empirical hypothesis based on the already established transformational cycle premise. This fact is sometimes forgotten in the case of (13). Consider three hypothetical languages: $L_{\{x\}}$, $L_{\{xy\}}$, and $L_{\{3s\}}$, each with phonological segments A, B, X, and Y, as well as lexical entries ABY, BAX. Assume that in each of these languages, B is realized as X before Y, and A is realized as Y before X. Thus, the grammars include the rules (a) and (3) as the most comprehensive statements of the facts.

Take note of how straightforward the transformative cycle principle is once more. It is intuitively stated that a predetermined set of procedures that take into account the form of a complex expression's constituents define its form. This is precisely exact thing one would anticipate from an interpretative hypothesis that applies to state markers, explicitly surface designs." (Morris Halle and Noam Chomsky, 1968) Getting back to genuine occasions, consider the more confounded phrases chalkboard eraser ("board eraser that is dark"), slate eraser ("eraser for a board"), and slate eraser ("eraser of a chalkboard"), with stress shapes 213, 132, and 312, separately.

Applying the previously mentioned rules to the surface construction of these structures. The principles being referred to, notwithstanding, are changes of an extremely limited and confined class, the class. (Morris Halle and Noam Chomsky, 1968)

Phonology is the investigation of the sound examples of human dialects. It is additionally the data that speakers have about the sound examples of their particular language (Fromkin and Rodman, 1988:69). The similarities between the phonologies of different languages outweigh the differences. Discourse sounds as actual elements can be endlessly different. However, they have very few uses as phonological units in a language (Maria Marlina, 1954).

Linguists are interested in the phonetic and phonological universals that are shared by all languages and the differences and similarities between sound systems. All human discourse sounds are described by similar tiny arrangement of phonetic characteristics or elements; similar class of these sounds are utilized in dialects spoken from the Cold Circle to the Cape of Good Expectation, and similar kinds of standard discourse sound examples exist everywhere. Victoria Fromkin expressed that as we procure a language, we realize which discourse sounds are available and the way in which they design as per standard norms (Maria Marlina, 1954).

This kind of language knowledge is the focus of phonology. Phonetics portrays discourse sounds, though phonology investigates how discourse sounds make frameworks and examples in human language. According to Maria Marlina (1954), the system and pattern of spoken sounds is referred to as the phonology of a language.

CONCLUSION

We frequently have intuitions about language without knowing where they came from or how to express them precisely, so phonological knowledge is not always accessible or discussable in depth. In any case, the information is without a doubt present. For instance, English speakers will by and large concur that the term snil is a possible yet non-existent word, while "fwil" is beyond the realm of possibilities (as the mark shows). In phonetic words, swil is an unexpected hole in the vocabulary, however fuil is an efficient hole brought about by English sound framework guidelines. Phonology is the investigation of how sounds are coordinated in language. Our investigation of phonology centers around two significant regions. The list of sounds a language has is one thing we think about. For instance, English has sounds which don't happen in French, as well as the other way around. This is a crucial area of study if one is

studying a language that has never been analyzed or written down before. Phonology is the investigation of the sound examples of human-language. It is additionally the sort of information that speakers have about the sound examples of their specific language (Fromkin and Rodman, 1988:69). Even though the phonologies of various languages around the world vary, there are more similarities than differences. Discourse sounds as actual substances might be boundlessly changed, however when they capability as components in a language, as phonological units, they are.

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